
Entrepreneurship Development and Wealth Creation in Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT: *The current poverty rate in Nigeria is more worrisome. It seems the recourse to massive entrepreneurial activities is now most preferable for an improved standard of living. As such, this study examines the relationship between entrepreneurship development and wealth creation in Ikot Ekpene senatorial district of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Methodologically, descriptive survey design was applied for this study. A Taro Yamane formula was utilized to determine the sample size of 334 out of 1009 population of SMEs from selected L. G. A. in Ikot Ekpene senatorial district using random sampling technique and Bowley's formula for proportionate representation and distribution of the structured questionnaire which was used to collect data from the respondents. The data collected were analyzed using Pearson's product moment correlation with the aid of SPSS. The findings revealed that entrepreneurship development has a positive significant relationship with wealth creation. It concluded that entrepreneurship development measured in terms of new business startups and business expansion promotes wealth creation in Ikot Ekpene senatorial district. As a recommendation, this study therefore encourages every Nigerian family to start at least one small business to supplement its income stream for wealth creation in the face of current economic downturn.*

KEYWORDS: Entrepreneur, Entrepreneurship development, Business startups, Business expansion, Poverty, Wealth creation.

INTRODUCTION

In the current Nigeria's economy, entrepreneurship development is more necessary than ever before. Starting a small business has become a viable alternative to the traditional employment that pays fixed amount of salary only ones in a month. As a business owner, you have the opportunity to earn on daily bases more than what you would have earned as an employee. This is because in business, one has absolute control over its stream of income and can determine its own salary, as well as re-investing profits back into the business to create more wealth and achieve financial freedom. This affirmed the position of Shehu (2021) who stated that the level of economic growth experienced by any environment is the function of the depth of small businesses within that environment.

Entrepreneurship development involves all activities geared towards the creation of a new venture, expansion and growth of an enterprise (Usoro & Brownson, 2023). It is concerned with the nurturing of the existing and potential entrepreneurs to become more efficient and effective in the management of small businesses. Wealth creation through entrepreneurship development is vital in the transformation of developing economies. This is obvious when considering the high level of economic growth recorded by the Asian countries like China, India, Malaysia, Indonesia, and so on. Nigeria as a developing economy requires massive entrepreneurial activities through new business startups, business growth, business expansion, and diversification of the existing businesses to stimulate economic development.

The general consensus is that small scale businesses under the direction of entrepreneurs are major contributors to economic growth and wealth creation. This view is corroborated by economists, scholars, politicians and many others. Hence, several countries are encouraging and promoting entrepreneurship development. Countries with increased entrepreneurial initiatives have experienced a greater reduction in poverty rate and a sustained increase in standard of living. To identify investable business opportunity in an environment is the most motivating factor for entrepreneurs. Entrepreneur constantly scans the environment for viable business opportunities that may exists in the form of societal problems and provide innovative ideas that can turn this problem into business venture (Allahar, 2021). Entrepreneur conceives this business opportunity, nurtures business idea(s) and puts together factors of production with the sole aim of making profit. However, it should be noted that in business there are competitions as a result of globalization. To succeed in the face of increasing competition, organizations need improved productivity at all levels (James et al., 2024). This requires commitment on the part of entrepreneurs. Through commitment, an entrepreneur may introduce important innovations by entering markets with a new product or new technology (Allahar, 2021).

Since wealth is the stock of assets that can contribute to people's well-being, creating wealth is important for increasing well-being. Wealth creation requires entrepreneurship development and financial literacy. Undisputedly, some of the important factors that greatly encourage economic backwardness of an individual or a nation are lack of entrepreneurial intention, inability to identify investable opportunity, and ineffective utilization of the abundant natural resources endowed in an environment (Miguel-Angel & Maria, 2014). With wealth, people could have the ability to maintain their lifestyle and life objectives for a lifetime (Abey Suriya, 2019). Greater wealth can create a more retirement security for oneself and better education opportunity for the next generation. It is logical to state that if the number of entrepreneurs of any given environment increases, then the poverty indicators will decrease (Ali & Ali, 2016). Therefore, there is urgent need for entrepreneurship development in Ikot Ekpene Senatorial district today more than ever, in order to create wealth for a better standard of living.

Statement to the problem

It is worrisome that Nigeria is currently tagged the world capital of poverty (World Poverty Clock, 2023) due to prevalent high rate of poverty in the country. More worrisome is the inability of the people of Ikot Ekpene senatorial district to create wealth through entrepreneurship even with the abundance of natural resources such as palm-fruit, vast fertile land, raffia, timber, huge population and so on. As could be seen in our society currently, the situation has gone out of hand with many of those who are willing to work cannot find gainful employment especially among the school leavers and graduates of tertiary institutions (NBS, 2023). As a result, many youths have taken to various crimes including banditry, prostitution, armed robbery, kidnapping, drug and child trafficking just to earn a living. It doesn't matter anymore whether the means are legitimate or not. The situation appears to have gone beyond remedy. Every year, new sets of graduates and school leavers add to the stock of unemployed youths resulting to increased frustration and aggression against the society that have failed to provide for them. Though several measures and efforts in form of palliative have been made by successive governments to combat the danger of poverty in Nigeria, it appears the efforts have no significant impact as poverty rate is on the increase on a daily basis.

Scholars have prescribed entrepreneurship as permanent remedy to the growing rate of poverty in Nigeria. But in spite of this, the sector has not been fully utilized. Entrepreneurship, despite being considered as the life wire of any economy are in Nigeria faced with many challenges such as: lack of start-up capital, obnoxious government policies on business, poor power supply, inexperience in business management on the part of most entrepreneur, and harsh banking policies for securing loans (Brownson, 2020; Agboli & Ukaegbu, 2006; Opafunso, & Okhankhuele, 2014). In an emerging market like Ikot Ekpene senatorial district with vast population, abundance of natural resources and human capital, entrepreneurship development is critical for wealth creation. It is against this background that the study seeks to examine the relationship between entrepreneurship development and wealth creation in Ikot Ekpene senatorial district of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study was to examine the relationship between entrepreneurship development and wealth creation in Ikot Ekpene senatorial district of Akwa Ibom State. The specific objectives include:

- i. To examine the relationship between new business startups and wealth creation in Ikot Ekpene senatorial district of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- ii. To investigate the relationship between business expansion and wealth creation in Ikot Ekpene senatorial district of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Research questions

To achieve the objectives of this study, the following research questions were raised:

- i. What is the relationship between new business startups and wealth creation in Ikot Ekpene senatorial district of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the relationship between business expansion and wealth creation in Ikot Ekpene senatorial district of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

Statement of hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for the study:

H₀₁: There is no positive significant relationship between new business startups and wealth creation in Ikot Ekpene senatorial district of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

Ho₂: There is no positive significant relationship between business expansion and wealth creation in Ikot Ekpene senatorial district of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

REVIEW OF RELEVANT LITERATURE

Conceptual framework

The diagram below depicts the relationship between independent variable and dependent variable. The concept of entrepreneurship development and its measures represents independent variable and the concept of wealth creation represents dependent variable.

Figure (1) Model of entrepreneurship development and wealth creation
Independent variable **Dependent variable**

Source: Researcher (2024)

The concept of entrepreneurship development

The concept of entrepreneurship dates back to many decades ago, highlighting persons who established commercial businesses for the purpose of generating profit by providing goods and services. Today, entrepreneurship is increasingly being viewed by practitioners and academics as a means of addressing economic and social challenges (Zacca & Dayan, 2017). It is referred to as the process of using private initiative to transform a business concept into a new venture or to expand and diversify an existing venture or enterprise with high growth potential (Prince et al., 2021). Thus, entrepreneurship is basically a process of creating value with risk taking mentality through either innovating new product or process or exploring new market. It is one of the fourth factors of production that aids in discovering new businesses that results to personal wealth creation through incomes generation, poverty reduction, and the promotion of economic growth, particularly in developing nations like Nigeria (Khuong & An, 2016). It's refers to the process of designing a new business, that is, a startup company offering a product, process or service (Reynold, 2015). Entrepreneurship is the application of creativity and innovation to solve problems and efforts to take advantage of opportunities. Entrepreneurship is the manifest ability and willingness of individuals, on their own, in teams, within and outside existing organizations to perceive and create new economic opportunities (new products, new production methods, and new market), and to introduce their ideas to the market in the face of uncertainty and other obstacles by making decisions on location, form and the use of resources and institutions.

An entrepreneur should be someone who has innovative ability to create something new and different, seeks opportunities, starts a business, takes risks, develops ideas and manages available resources to succeed. They are agents that overcome obstacles to build their enterprises in an entrepreneurial relationship by being change agents through recognition of opportunities, exploring it through innovation and creativity (Ajuluchukwu &

Okute, 2020). Entrepreneurship development has been conceived by successive Nigerian government as a program of activities to enhance the knowledge, skills, behaviour and attitude of individual and group to assume the role of entrepreneurs (Usono & Brownson, 2023; Osemeke, 2012). It involves the ability to identify business opportunities and the willingness to initiate and sustain appropriate actions towards the actualization of business objectives. Brownson (2014b) stated that the concept of entrepreneurship development involves all activities geared towards the creation of a new venture, expansion and growth of an enterprise. It aims to enlarge the base of entrepreneurs in order to hasten the pace at which new ventures are created. All over the world, entrepreneurship development is now being considered as a panacea to remedy some of the entrenched socio-economic challenges facing the modern state. This has strengthened the argument for greater entrepreneurial culture in a developing country like Nigeria. It therefore seems that the recourse to entrepreneurship development for wealth creation and economic survival is essential. It is now regarded as the magic bullet that can remedy some of the embedded socio-economic challenges facing the modern state such as poverty, unemployment, falling standards of living. Entrepreneurship development focuses on the individual who wishes to start or expand a business. Entrepreneurship development contributes to wealth creation when it creates employment through the startup of new business or the expansion of existing ones and it increases social wealth by creating new markets, new industries, new technology, new institutional forms, new jobs.

In a bid to promote entrepreneurship development in the country, the federal government of Nigeria created certain policies and agencies like Manufacturers Association of Nigeria (MAN), National Association of Small and Medium Enterprises (NASME), Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN), National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP), Small and Medium Industries Equity Investment Scheme (SMIEIS), Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) etc, to help in one way or the other in promoting entrepreneurship. It is for individuals or groups to take advantage of this and the abundant of natural resources with emerging market in Nigeria to develop entrepreneurship for wealth creation. It is logically to state that the wealth of any given country increase when its number of entrepreneurs increases.

New business startups

Entrepreneurial visions must be transformed into intentions, which in turn are the starting point for new business start-up. New business startups are the output of the passion and determination of entrepreneurs (Angadi & Patil, 2021). It is an entrepreneurial profit oriented venture that did not formerly exist as an organization, built for rapid growth in extreme uncertainty and aimed at bringing to market an innovative product or service that benefits a significant customer base economically and socially (Davies, 2022). It is a newly born company without previous history of operations (Hyytinen, Pajarinen, & Rouvinen, 2015). Business startup is defined as a human institution designed to create new products or services for profit under extreme uncertainty (Ries, 2011).

According to Teodensia (2022) new small businesses create jobs and introduce new technologies, boosting the production of goods and services thereby stimulating wealth creation, economic growth and development. These new business enterprises have a very important and positive impact on employment generation, poverty alleviation, and socio-economic development (Syed Zaheer Abba & Andras, 2017). They are considered the sources of most new jobs generated in an economy, they bring about the creation of new industries and markets, and they develop and introduce innovative products and services and

provide new solutions to economic, social and environmental problems (Shepherd & Patzelt, 2021).

Business expansion

Business expansion is essential mostly when the business has reach maturity stage in a firm's life cycle (Udu & Ujebe, 2018). Enterprise can expand in size or the range of business that they pursue. Expansion is when firms' operations increases by adding markets, products, services, or stages of production to the existing business.

Nowadays, organizations operate in unpredictable environment which forces them to respond by screening the environment and adopt strategies that position them viable in the market. One of these strategies is business expansion. At this point, the firm is well established in a place and now wants to expand either geographically or in content. Geographical expansion means establishing new offices, branches, plants or depots in another environment, while content expansion means increasing product or service variety either within one office / plant or in many offices / plants (Udu & Ujebe, 2018). By expanding to new geographical locations, companies can access new markets and customers, diversify their revenue streams, and gain a competitive advantage over other players in the industry (Thirathon & Meeprom, 2020). In order to be effective while growing, businesses must respond to the opportunities, challenges, risks and limitations posed by the external environment.

Business expansion is meant to add value to the firm in terms of customer satisfaction and performance. The purpose of expansion is to allow the company to enter lines of business that are different from current operations. Enterprise can expand in size or the range of business that they pursue. Expansion strategy may become fanciful because of any or a combination of the following: growth in size of customers, clients, consumers; a means of competitive struggle and; increase in market size and control. Expansion and other similar terms used in the business and corporate strategy literature do not always mean market expansion. For instance, Omri (2020) suggest concentration, integration, diversification, cooperation, and internationalization as different routes to expansion. But these strategies do not necessarily lead to expansion of market for a particular product category.

There are three theories associated with expansion. These are Concentric, Horizontal and Conglomerate expansion. In the concentric expansion, the organization adds new products or services which have technological or commercial synergies with current products and which will appeal to new customer groups. The objective is therefore to benefit from synergy effects due to the complementarities of activities, and thus to expand the firm's market by attracting new groups of buyers. In the horizontal expansion the organization adds new products or services that are technologically or commercially unrelated to current products, but which may appeal to current customers. In a competitive environment, this form of expansion is desirable if the present customers are loyal to the current products and if the new products are of good quality and are well promoted and priced. Moreover, the new products are marketed to the same economic environment as the existing products, which may lead to rigidity and instability. In other words, this strategy tends to increase the firm's dependence on certain market segments (Thirathon & Meeprom, 2020). In the conglomerate expansion, the organization markets new products or services that have no technological or commercial synergies with current products, but which may appeal to new groups of customers. The conglomerate expansion has little relationship with the firm's current business. The strategies of expansion may seek internal development of new products or markets, acquisition of a firm, alliance with a complementary company, licensing of new

technologies, and distributing or importing a products line manufactured by another firm (Udu & Ujebe, 2018).

The Concept of wealth creation

Wealth is created either directly or indirectly by the government or by individuals who perceived a need that will solve the problem of humanity. As an entrepreneur, creating wealth means building a profitable business that generates profits for the owner and increases in value over time. Omri (2020) asserts that entrepreneurship create wealth for individuals who possess different competencies that will sustain the venture for tomorrow's generation. Wealth creation is measured by the quantity of your assets, its growth and sustainability. The critical components coincide with McClelland's (1961) psychological makeup, "the need for achievement". Entrepreneurship allows improved rural livelihoods when the businesses established make it possible for individuals and families to increase their income and eventually start to acquire assets (create wealth). Okoye-Nebo et al. (2014) argued that wealth creation reduces unemployment, poverty and eliminate social vices in the society. As a business owner, you have the opportunity to earn more than you would as an employee. This is because you have control over your income and can determine your own salary, as well as reinvest profits back into the business to fuel growth.

Relationship between entrepreneurship development and wealth creation

One of the major reasons that individuals tend to become entrepreneurs is because they are unable to find suitable and secured jobs. As a result, by being enterprising, creative and finding market, not only are they able to generate income for themselves but also create wealth through their businesses. Multiple scholars emphasized upon importance of entrepreneurship development and its linkage with economic growth and wealth creation of the country (Kim et al., 2022).

New business startup and wealth creation

In the face of current economic downturn where take home pay of average Nigeria worker hardly take him home, every Nigerian family is encouraged to supplement its income by starting one form of small business or the other. Civil servants and factory workers are not left out of the struggle to earn additional income through entrepreneurial activities. New business startups are innovative commercial ventures built for rapid and explosive economic growth and wealth creation (Davies, 2022). It is believed that a strong and vibrant economy is driven by large pool of small scale businesses, each contributing a sizeable proportion to expand economic base of the country. The federal government of Nigeria and indeed most state governments have come to the realization that one of the ways to strengthen economy is through entrepreneurship development. As such, governments constantly vary their policies in a manner that allows the establishment of small businesses. This was obvious in the activity of the last administration of Akwa Ibom State government led by His Excellency, Udom Emmanuel to reignite entrepreneurial spirit through the establishment of many small scale businesses in the State as a pathway to economic development and wealth creation. This movement was a clear indication of the overwhelming importance of entrepreneurship development in economic transformation and sustenance of a particular society.

Business expansion and wealth creation

Business expansion is an investor's sole purpose to maximize wealth. The existence of different revenue sources allows organizations to avoid capital and liquidity problems (Davies, 2022). Entrepreneurship development contributes to wealth creation when it creates employment through the startup of new business or the expansion of existing ones and they

increase social wealth by creating new markets, new industries, new technology, new institutional forms, new jobs and net increases in real productivity, increases income which culminates in higher standards of living for the population. It is logically to state that if the number of entrepreneurs of any given country increase the poverty indicators will decrease. Expansion strategy may become fanciful because of growth in size of customers, clients, consumers; a means of competitive struggle and; increase in market size and control. By expanding to new geographical locations, companies can access new markets and customers, diversify their revenue streams, and gain a competitive advantage over other players in the industry (Thirathon & Meeprom, 2020). This is relational to wealth creation.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey design was applied for this study. Using Taro Yamane formula, the sample size was determined to 334 out of 1009 population of SMEs from Ikot Ekpene senatorial district with a random sampling technique and Bowley's formula for proportionate representation and distribution of the structured questionnaire which was used to collect data from the respondents. After the administration of 334 copies of the questionnaire, 321 were returned in a usable form. The analysis in this study was done using the copies of the questionnaire that was returned. Pearson's Product Moment Correlations (PPMC) analysis was applied in analyzing the generated primary data for the study. The rationale for this choice of data analytical tool is to show the causal relationship between the studied variables.

Data Analysis

In the analysis of data, it becomes imperative to subject data to statistical test to ascertain the extent of deviation or agreements with the hypotheses formulated in the introductory part of this study. The Pearson's product moment correlation coefficient was used to measure the strength of the relationship between the variables. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 levels of significance. The null hypotheses will be rejected if the probability value (p-value) is less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$).

Table 1: Pearson's product moment correlations analysis

		New business startups	Business expansion	Wealth creation
New business startups	Pearson Correlation	1	.674**	.894**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	321	321	321
Business expansion	Pearson Correlation	.832**	654	.856**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	1	.000
	N	321	321	321
Wealth creation	Pearson Correlation	.894**	.856**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	321	321	321

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Source: Field survey data (2024)

Test of hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no positive significant relationship between new business startups and wealth creation in Ikot Ekpene senatorial district of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

From the analysis in table 1, the correlation coefficient (R) for hypothesis one (H_{01}) is $R_{x_1} = 0.894$, suggesting a strong positive correlation between new business startups and wealth creation. The result was statistically significant ($R_{x_1} = 0.894$; $n = 321$; $p = 0.000$). The implication is that, starting a new business will serve as another source of income. Based on this, it is safe to assume that new business startups will influence wealth creation. Since the p-value is less than 0.05 ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is a positive significant relationship between new business startups and wealth creation.

H₀₂: There is no positive significant relationship between business expansion and wealth creation in Ikot Ekpene senatorial district of Akwa Ibom State?

From the analysis in table 1, the correlation coefficient (R) for hypothesis three (H_{03}) is $R_{x_3} = 0.856$, suggesting a strong positive correlation between business expansion and wealth creation. The result was statistically significant ($R_{x_3} = 0.856$; $n = 321$; $p = 0.000$). The implication is that, as the business expands with more branches, so does income base increases. Based on this, it is safe to assume that business expansion will influence wealth creation. Since the p-value is less than 0.05 ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is a positive significant relationship between business expansion and wealth creation.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

New business startups and wealth creation

The result of hypothesis one in table 1 shows that the correlation between new business startups and wealth creation in Ikot Ekpene senatorial district ($R_{x_1} = 0.894$; $n = 321$; $p = 0.000$) is positive and significant. This finding prompted the rejection of the null hypothesis, while the alternative hypothesis was accepted. The importance of this finding is that, starting a new business will serve as another source of income. This result supports what Teodensia (2022) meant when he observed that new small businesses create jobs and introduce new technologies, boosting the production of goods and services thereby stimulating wealth creation, economic growth and development. By this, it is assumed that new business startups will influence wealth creation in Ikot Ekpene senatorial district.

Business expansion and wealth creation

Objective two of the study was to assess the relationship between business expansion and wealth creation in Ikot Ekpene senatorial district. From the analysis of hypothesis two in table 1 above, the result showed a correlation coefficient (r) value of ($R_{x_3} = 0.856$; $n = 321$; $p = 0.000$) which was statistically positive. The null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative accepted that there is a positive significant relationship between business expansion and wealth creation in Ikot Ekpene senatorial district. The importance of this finding is that, as the business expands with more branches, so does income base increases. This finding is in line with the opinion expressed by Thirathon & Meepprom (2020), and Davies (2022) that expanding to new geographical locations, companies can access new markets and customers, diversify their revenue streams, and gain a competitive advantage over other players in the industry thereby avoiding capital and liquidity problems. Also, as stated by Cameron & Whetton (2019) concentric expansion where organization adds new products or services which have technological or commercial synergies with current products and can appeal to new customer groups, the objective which is to benefit from synergy effects due to the complementarities of activities, and thus expand the firm's market by attracting new groups of buyers is important to wealth creation to the entrepreneur. Meanwhile, as stated by Udu &

Ujebe (2018) business expansion is essential mostly when the business has reach maturity stage in a firm's life cycle.

CONCLUSION

From the findings made in this study, it is quite safe to conclude that starting a new business with efficient and effective management to grow and expand will serve as a good recipe for poverty alleviation and wealth creation. Based on these findings, it is concluded that entrepreneurship development has positive significant relationship with wealth creation in Ikot Ekpene senatorial district of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the major findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. That in the face of current economic downturn, every Nigerian family is encouraged to start a small business to supplement its income, combat poverty and create wealth.
- ii. That entrepreneur should adopt concentric expansion strategy where organization adds new products or services which have technological or commercial synergies with current products or services due to the complementarities of activities, and thus expand the firm's market by attracting new groups of customers.

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